

ON K -FACTORIALS AND SMARANDACHEIALS

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Abstract F. Smarandache defines a k -factorial as $n(n-k)(n-2k)\dots$, terminating when $n-xk$ is positive and $n-(x+1)k$ is 0 or negative. Smarandacheials extend this definition into the negative numbers such that the factorial terminates when $|n-xk|$ is less than or equal to n and $|n-(x+1)k|$ is greater than n . This paper looks at some relations between these numbers.

Keywords: Smarandache function; Additive Analogue; Mean value formula.

k -factorials

We begin by looking at the k -factorial, represented by k exclamation marks after the variable.

The k -factorial is merely the full factorial $n!$ with some of the terms omitted.

e.g. the factorial for $n = 8$;

$$n! = 8! = 8.7.6.5.4.3.2.1$$

If we look at the 2-factorial $n!!$, we have

$$n!! = 8.6.4.2$$

and we see that 7, 5, 3 and 1 are not present.

Similarly the 3-factorial $n!!!$ gives

$$n!!! = 8.5.2$$

and 7, 6, 4, 2 and 1 are not present.

In the first case we have 7!! omitted, so we may write $n!! = n! | (n-1)!!$

For the 3-factorial, there are two sequences present, 7!!! and 6!!!, so

$$n!!! = n! | [(n-1)!!!(n-2)!!!]$$

Using the notation $n!_k$ for a k -factorial, we can easily obtain the general formula

$$n!_k = \frac{n!}{\prod_{i=1}^{k-1} (n-i)!_k}$$

A PARI/GP program to implement this is

```
{
kfactorial(n, k)=local(result);
result=n!;
for(i = 1, k - 1,result/=kfactorial(n - i, k));
result
```

```

}
although this is highly ineffective and not recommended for use.
To access the k-factorial function use

```

```

{
kfactorial(n, k)=local(res);
res=vector(n, i, if (i <= k, i, 0));
for (i = k + 1, n, res[i]=i*res[i - k]);
res[n];
}

```

This code stores 1 to k in a vector in positions 1 to k . Then each progressive term is calculated from the k -th previous entry and the current one. The above code actually calculates $n!_k$ for all n from 1 to n .

Even simpler, and the quickest yet is

```

{
kf(n,k)=local(r,c);
c=n
if (c==0,c=k);
r=c;
while (c<n,c+=k;r*=c);
r
}

```

The r variable holds the result, and the c variable is a counter. c is set to $n \bmod k$, and then incremented until it is n . r is multiplied by c at each stage.

We can also see that if $\gcd(n, k) = k$, then $n!_k = k^{\frac{n}{k}} (\frac{n}{k})!$, so in this case we have

$$k^{\frac{n}{k}} (\frac{n}{k})! \prod_{i=1}^{k-1} (n - k)_k = n!$$

If $\gcd(n, k) \neq k$, then the k -factorial seems more difficult to define. We address this problem shortly.

Smarandacheials

In extending the k -factorial to the negative integers, we need to further define the parameters involved.

If we let n be the starting number, and k be the decrease, then we also need to define m as $n \bmod k$, and then $m' = k - m$.

If m is greater than or equal to m' , we can see that $SM(n, k) = \pm [n!_k * (n - (m - m'))!_k]$.

If m is less than m' , then we have $SM(n, k) = \pm [n!_k * (n - (m - m') - k)!_k]$.

The plus/minus sign is not known yet - this is developed later in this paper.

This result follows because m represents the last integer from $n!_k$, and so $k - m$ will be the first negative integer from $(n - x)!_k$, and so we determine x .

If m is greater than or equal to m' , then the difference $n - (n - x)$ must be the difference between m and m' , so $x = m - m'$.

If $m < m'$, then we have a problem. The basic idea still works, however the negative factorial will rise to a higher level than the original n , and this is not

allowed. So the adjustment from subtracting k cuts the last negative integer out of the equation.

To combine these, define m^* as the smallest positive value of $(m - m') \bmod k$, and now we may write;

$$SM(n, k) = \pm [n!_k^*(n - m^*)!_k].$$

For an example, consider $SM(13, 5)$. Then $m = 3$ and $m' = 2$, and $m^* = (3 - 2) \bmod 5 = 1$, so we get;

$$\begin{aligned} SM(13, 5) &= \pm 13!_5^*(13 - 1)!_5 \\ &= \pm 13!_5^*(12)!_5 \\ &= \pm 13.8.3^*12.7.2 \end{aligned}$$

However, for $SM(12, 5)$, $m^* = (2 - 3) \bmod 5 = 4$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \pm 12!_5^*(12 - 4)!_5 \\ &= \pm 12!_5^*8!_5 \\ &= \pm 12.7.2^*8.3 \end{aligned}$$

The sign is then simply $(-1)^{\wedge}(\text{number of terms in second Smarandacheial})$.

Number of terms in $n!_k$

Given $n!_k$, the expansion of the expression is;

$$n(n - k) \cdots (n - ak)$$

So there are $a + 1$ terms.

Using a simple example, e.g. for $k = 5$, we can construct a table of the number of terms;

n	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
no. of terms	1	2	2	2	2	2	3

n	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
no. of terms	3	3	3	3	4	4	4

From this we see that there are $\text{ceil}(\frac{n}{k})$ terms.

Therefore a full expression for the Smarandacheial function is

$$SM(n, k) = (-1)^{\wedge} \left[\frac{n - m^*}{k} \right] n!_k^*(n - m^*)!_k$$

$n!_k$ for $\text{gcd}(n, k) < k$

In this case, we have no easy relation. We can however spot an interesting and deep relation with these k -factorials - their relation to a neighbouring $n!_k$ with $\text{gcd}(n, k) = k$.

To demonstrate this connection, we will examine $15!_5$.

This is $15.10.5 = 750$.

Now $16!_5$ is 16.11.6.1. There seems to be nothing else we can do.
However, we can write this as;

$$\left(\frac{16}{15}\right) \left(\frac{11}{10}\right) \left(\frac{6}{5}\right) 15!_5$$

Still nothing, but then we see that $\frac{16}{15} = 1 + \frac{1}{15}$, and so on, and so we get;

$$\left(1 + \frac{1}{15}\right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{10}\right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{5}\right) 15!_5$$

If we expand the brackets, hey presto (I have skipped a few steps here)

$$16!_5 = 15!_5 + 15.10 + 15.5 + 10.5 + 15 + 10 + 5 + 1$$

This is generalizable into

$$(n+x)!_k = \left[n!_k + \sum_{d \in S} \frac{x^{d_i} n!_k}{d} \right] x$$

where x is less than k , S is the distinct power set of components of $n!_k$ (e.g. for $15!_5$, $S = 15, 10, 5$), and d_i is the number of elements of S involved in d .

For example, $18!_5$ gives

$$18!_5 = [15!_5 + 3(15.10 + 15.5 + 10.5) + 9(15 + 10 + 5) + 27]^*3$$

$18!_6 = 5616$, and the sum on the RHS is

$$750 + 825 + 270 + 27 = 1872, \text{ and } 1872^*3 = 5616.$$

References

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